

Variations of Fissures and Lobes in Human Lungs: A Cadaveric Study**Sudarshana Smita**

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Abstract:

Introduction: Accurate knowledge of variations in the fissures and lobes of the lungs is of paramount importance for cardiothoracic surgeons to perform lobectomies, segmental resection of the infected bronchopulmonary segments, and to lessen post-operative complications like air leaks. Likewise, it is equally important for radiologists to correctly interpretate Chest-X-ray, CT scans MRIs of the chest.

Aim: To observe and describe the variation in fissures and lobes in human lungs.

Material and Methods: The study was conducted on 54 lungs (28 right and 26 left), well preserved in formalin, from various medical colleges of Patna, Bihar. A gross examination was done to find out the presence of incomplete oblique fissures of the right and left lungs; incomplete horizontal fissures of the right lung; along with their grades. The absence of a horizontal fissure in the right lung and the presence of accessory fissures were also observed. Photographs of the observed variations were taken. The Percentages of the variations were calculated and compared with the previous studies.

Result: Among the right-sided lungs, complete oblique fissures and complete horizontal fissures were found in 28.5% (8/28) and 35.7% (10/28) respectively. Four out of twenty-six (15.3%) left-sided lungs had complete oblique fissures. Incomplete oblique fissures and incomplete horizontal fissures in right-sided lungs were found in 71.4% (20/28) and 42.8% (12/28) respectively. 84.6% (22/26) of the left-sided lungs had incomplete oblique fissures. Absence of oblique fissure was not found in any of the lungs examined (0/54), while 21.5 % (6/28) of the right-sided lungs had absent horizontal fissure. Left median fissure, a type of accessory fissure, were found in 6 out of 26 lungs examined (23.1%).

Conclusion: The present study has found high percentages of incomplete oblique fissures; low percentages of complete oblique fissures and complete horizontal fissures; compared to many studies done so far. This highlights the possibilities of a wider range of variations and necessitates more research to find out the extend of variations.

Keywords: Oblique fissure, Horizontal fissure, Left median fissure, Accessory fissure, Lung.

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Introduction

Lungs are the vital organs for respiration located on either side of the mediastinum in the thorax. It has the main function of oxygenating the deoxygenated blood by bringing it into close relation with the venous blood in the pulmonary capillaries. The lung consists of an apex, base, 3 surfaces, and 3 borders. The lung has costal, mediastinal, and diaphragmatic surfaces.

Normally, the right lung has three lobes (superior, middle, and inferior), separated by two fissures: oblique and horizontal. The left lung has two lobes (superior and inferior), separated by a horizontal fissure (Standring, 2005) [1]. The oblique fissure runs from the inferior border of the lung in a super posterior direction until it meets the posterior lung border, while the horizontal fissure runs horizontally from the sternum at the level of the 4th rib to meet the oblique fissure. The fissures permit uniform expansion of the entire lungs during respiration. The fissures may be complete or incomplete, thus

dividing the lungs into complete and incomplete lobes. The fissures are complete when the lobes are joined together only at the hilum.

Since the fissures form the boundaries of the lobes of the lungs, accurate knowledge of their position is essential to appreciate the lobar anatomy and locating bronchopulmonary segments of the lungs [2]. The clinical significance of the anatomical variations in fissures and lobes of the lungs lies in the fact that surgeons have to be well acquainted with the location of bronchopulmonary segments to: accurately diagnose, plan, and perform lobectomies; to do segmental resection of the infected bronchopulmonary segments, and to lessen post-operative complication like air leaks. Besides this, it is important to perform bronchoscopic procedures. Likewise, knowledge of variations and fissures of the lungs is equally significant for radiologists to: correctly interpretate pleural effusion; to assess the

spread of the diseases, and to recognize the atypical presentation of lung diseases [3].

This study aims to provide further insights into the extent of variations reported in the studies done so far.

Objective: To observe and describe the variations in fissures and lobes along with their patterns in human lungs collected from cadavers.

Methodology: The study was carried out in the department(s) of anatomy of the three medical colleges of Patna, Bihar: Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), Nalanda Medical College and Hospital (NMCH), and Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (IGIMS). Before starting the study, approval from the concerned ethical committee, and due permission of the heads of the department of anatomy of the respective medical colleges were taken. Formalin fixed cadaveric lungs preserved in department's museums and the lungs obtained from the cadavers available for undergraduate dissection classes were examined meticulously for the following:

1. The pattern of lobes and fissures
2. Variations in fissures and lobes and
3. Presence of accessory fissures and lobes if any

After that, photographs of the lungs examined were taken. A total of 54 lungs (28 right and 26 left lung) of unknown age and sex were included in the study. 2 left lungs were excluded from the study since it was damaged.

Lungs examined were categorized into following four grades based on degree of completeness of fissures according to anatomical classification proposed by Craig and Walker. [4]

Grade I - Complete fissure with entirely separated lobes;

Grade II- Complete visceral cleft but parenchymal fusion at the base of fissure;

Grade III- Visceral cleft evident for a part of fissure and

Grade IV being the complete fusion of lobes with no evident fissural line.

In other words, Grade I of Craig & Walker classification mean presence of complete fissure, while Grade II and Grade III signify incomplete fissures. Grade IV indicates the absence of fissure. Percentages of the observed variations were calculated using Microsoft excel and compared with the previous studies.

Results

Table 1 describes the findings of the variations of various fissures in present study. Among the right-sided lungs, complete oblique fissure (Fig.1) and complete horizontal fissure (Fig.2) were found in 28.5% (8/28) and 35.7% (10/28) respectively. Similarly, 15.3% (4/26) of left- sided lungs had complete oblique fissure (Fig.3). Incomplete oblique fissure (Fig.4) and incomplete horizontal fissure (Fig.5&6) in the right- sided lungs were found to be high at 71.4% (20/28) and 42.8% (12/28) respectively. 84.6% (22/26) of the left -sided lungs had incomplete oblique fissure (Fig.7). Absence of oblique fissure was not found in any of the lungs examined (0/54), while 21.5 % (6/28) of the right sided lungs had absent horizontal fissure (Fig.8). Left median fissure, a type of accessory fissure in left lung, was found in 6 out of 26 lungs examined (23.1%) as shown in Fig.9. The lobe of azygous vein which is a type of accessory lobe of right lung (Fig.10), was found in 3.57% (1/28) of the samples.

Table 1: Variations of fissures of lungs

Right Lung[N=28]	Complete Fissure	Incomplete Fissure	Absent
Oblique Fissure	8[28.57%]	20[71.43%]	0[0%]
Horizontal Fissure	10[35.71%]	12[42.85%]	6[21.42%]
Left Lung[N=26]			
Oblique Fissure	4[15.38%]	22[84.61%]	0[0%]

According to Craig & Walker's classification, out of 28 right lungs examined, oblique fissures were found to belong to following various grades: Grade I-8 (28.5%); Grade II- 10(35.7%); Grade III-10(35.7%); and Grade IV- 0(0%), while among the 26 left lungs examined, oblique fissure belonged to Grade I- 4 (15.4. %); Grade II- 14(53.8%); Grade III- 08(30.7%); and Grade IV- 0(0%) respectively as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Patterns of oblique fissures of lungs according to Craig & Walker

Lung	Oblique Fissure (Number (%))				
	Grade I (%)	Grade II (%)	Grade III (%)	Grade IV (%)	Total (%)
Right	8(28.5%)	10(35.7%)	10(35.7%)	0(0%)	28(100%)
Left	4(15.4%)	14(53.8%)	08(30.7%)	0(0%)	26(100%)

Horizontal fissure of right lung was found to belong to Grade I- 10 (35.7%); Grade II- 02(7.1%); Grade III- 10(35.7%); and Grade IV -06(21.4%) respectively as detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Patterns of horizontal fissures of lung according to Craig& Walker

Lung	Horizontal Fissure (Number (%))				
	Grade I (%)	Grade II (%)	Grade III (%)	Grade IV (%)	Total (%)
Right	10(35.7%)	02(7.1%)	10(35.7%)	06(21.4%)	28(100%)

Figure 1: Right lung with complete oblique fissure and entirely separated lobes (Grade I) on the mediastinal surface

Figure 2: Right lung with complete horizontal fissure with entirely separated lobes (Grade I) on the costal surface

Figure 3: Left lung with complete oblique fissure and entirely separated lobes (Grade I) on the mediastinal surface

Figure 4: Right lung with incomplete oblique fissure (Grade III) with visceral cleft present in part of the fissure on the costal surface

Figure 5: Right lung with incomplete horizontal fissure on the mediastinal surface (Grade II); complete visceral cleft present but parenchymal fusion at the base of fissure

Figure 6: Right lung with incomplete horizontal fissure on the costal surface (Grade III): with visceral cleft present in part of the fissure

Figure 7: Left lung with incomplete oblique fissure (Grade II) on the mediastinal surface with complete visceral cleft but parenchymal fusion at the base of fissure

Figure 8: Right lung with complete absence of horizontal fissure (Grade IV). Fissure shown is of complete oblique fissure

Figure 9: Left median fissure (Accessory fissure in left lung)

Figure 10: Lobe of Azgov vein (Accessory lobe) in right lung

Discussion

Variations of lobes and fissures of the lungs take place due to defects in its normal development during the embryonic period [5]. Accessory fissures could be the result of the non-obliteration of spaces that normally are obliterated.[6]. Detection of any accessory fissure is indicative of the persistence of prenatal fissure.[7]. The identification of the completeness of the fissures is significant before lobectomy because incomplete fissures in individuals are more likely to develop postoperative air leaks [8], necessitating further corrective procedures such as stapling and pericardial sleeves. Likewise, incomplete fissures may mimic pleural effusion in chest X-rays and cause the odd appearance of fluid tracking within the fissure. Furthermore, if there is an incomplete fissure,

pneumonia, and carcinoma of the lung may spread through the incomplete fissures of the lung to other lobes.[8] The gradation of fissures is essential for the surgeon as they have to approach to ligate the vessels and bronchi through the depth of the fissure. Grade 1 oblique fissure facilitates the approach while doing lobectomy and Video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery.[9]. But when the fissures are incomplete, lung parenchyma has to be dissected to reach these structures which can lead to intraoperative hemorrhage and more postoperative complications [10].

Several studies have been conducted to find out the variations in the lobes of the lungs so far. The prevalence of the various types of fissures of the lungs found by previous authors has been compared

with the present study and is detailed above in Table -4.

Table 4: Comparison of results of the previous studies on variations of pulmonary fissures with the present study

Side	Fissure	Type	Ambali [16] 2014 [n=100]	Varalakshmi [12] 2014 [n=64]	Thapa [13] 2016 [n=40]	Gopalkrishna [14] 2017 [n=100]	Shivleela [11] 2017 [n=84]	Sudikshya [15] 2008 [n=46]	Shiv Kumar [17] 2019 [n=60]	Present Study 2020 [n=54]
Right	Oblique	Complete	82% (41/50)	83.3% (25/30)	70% (14/20)	84% (42/50)	32% (12/38)	69.57% (16/23)	63.33% (19/30)	28.57% (8/28)
		Incomplete	14% (7/50)	16.7% (5/30)	30% (6/20)	14% (7/50)	63% (24/38)	30.4% (7/23)	36% (11/30)	71.4% (20/28)
		Absent	4% (2/50)	0% (0/30)	0% (0/20)	2% (1/50)	5% (2/38)	0% (0/23)	0% (0/30)	0% (0/28)
		Complete	64% (32/50)	60% (18/30)	30% (6/20)	74% (37/50)	10% (4/38)	52.18% (12/23)	16.66% (5/30)	35.71% (10/28)
	Horizontal	Incomplete	28% (14/50)	30% (9/30)	50% (10/20)	22% (11/50)	63% (24/38)	34% (8/23)	70% (21/30)	42.85% (12/28)
		Absent	8% (4/50)	10% (3/30)	20% (4/20)	4% (2/50)	26% (10/38)	13.04% (3/23)	13.3% (4/30)	21.42% (6/28)
		Complete	64% (32/50)	67.6% (23/34)	60% (12/20)	82% (41/50)	70% (38/46)	48.15% (11/23)	46.66% (14/30)	15.38% (4/26)
Left	Oblique	Incomplete	8% (16/50)	29.4% (10/34)	25% (5/20)	16% (8/50)	9% (4/46)	51.8% (12/23)	46.66% (14/30)	84.6% (22/26)
		Absent	4% (2/50)	3% (1/34)	15% (3/20)	2% (1/50)	9% (4/46)	0% (0/23)	6.6% (2/30)	0% (0/26)

Complete fissure in right lungs in this study was noticeably low at 28.5% compared to many studies [12,13,14,15,16,17] (Table-5), but is close to the findings of Shiv Leela et al [11] (32%). Incomplete oblique fissure (grade II and grade III) in the right lung was found in 71.4% of the samples, which is much higher than most of the studies [12,13,14,15,16,17] (Table-5). However, the findings of the Shiv Leela et al [11] were very close (63%) to that observed in this study. Absent oblique fissure in the right lung (grade IV) was not found in the present study, which was very similar to most of the studies described [12,13,15,17].

The percentage of complete horizontal fissures in the right lungs in the present study was 35.7 which is much lower than that reported by many studies. [12,14,15,16,17] (Table-5), but is close (30%) to the findings of Thapa et al [13]. Incomplete horizontal fissure (grade II and grade III) in right lung was found in 42.85%, which is close to the findings of Thapa et al [13] who reported in 50% of the samples. However, the observation of Gopalkrishna et al [14] was lower at 22%, and that of Shiv Leela et al [11] (63%) and Kumar Shiv et al

[17] (70%) were much higher compared to the present study. Absent horizontal fissures in the right lung (grade IV) in this study was 21.42%, which is nearly similar to the findings of Thapa et al. [13], who found this in 20% of the samples. However, Ambali et al. [16] and Gopalkrishna et al. [14] reported absent horizontal fissures in 8% and 4% of the lungs, respectively. Complete horizontal fissures in the left lung in this study was in 15.3% of the samples, which is much lower than that reported by many studies [11,12,13,14,15,16,17], (Table-5). Incomplete oblique fissure (grade II and grade III) in the left lung was found to be very high at 84.6%, while in the studies by Sudikshya et al [15] and Kumar Shiv et al [17], it was reported in 51.8% and 46.6% respectively. In contrast, Gopalkrishna et al [14] reported the same in only 8% of the samples. Absent oblique fissures (grade IV) in the left lung were not found in the present study. Similarly, Sudikshya et al [15] also did not find the presence of absent oblique fissure in their study. However, Thapa et al [13] and Kumar Shiv et al [17] reported the same in 15% and 6.6% of the samples respectively.

Several studies claimed the presence of accessory fissures of the lungs (Esomonu et al. [18], 2013. Mayuri et al. [19], 2013). George et al. [20], 2014 reported that 3 (4.61%) of the right lungs and 2 (2.73%) of the left lungs had accessory fissures. However, in the present study, left median fissure (accessory fissure of left lung) was found in 6 out of 26 left lungs (23.1%), a finding close to that reported by Jacob & Pillay [21] (27.7 %) and Lanka Rana-weera et al [22] (16.6%), but much higher than that observed by George et al. [20] (2.73%). Azygous lobe or lobe of azygous vein is a normal anatomical variant present in only 1% cases. It is present in right lung in superomedial aspect, formed due to invagination of azygous vein into the mediastinal surface of the lung due to delayed migration of right posterior cardinal vein in embryonic period which results in to part of the lung bud going medial to right posterior cardinal vein. Double fold of visceral pleura goes along with the vein to produce an accessory fissure called azygous fissure through which it is separated from superior lobe of right lung. [23] It is not true lobe as it does not have separate bronchopulmonary segment, but has clinical significance as it mimic bullae, lung tumor, pneumothorax. Noticeably, lobe of azygous vein (accessory lobe of right lung) was found in 3.57% of the lungs examined in the present study which is similar to the study conducted by Biswas KK et al [24] (2.17%) but meaningfully higher than the studies done by Anson BJ et al [25], Boyden EA [26], Rauf A et al [27], who reported the same in 0.43%, 0.2% and 0.57% of the samples respectively.

Limitation

Owing to small sample size and descriptive design of the study with the objective of finding the percentage of the variations in studied samples, the findings of the study cannot be extrapolated to larger population.

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Conclusion:

In the present study, the findings of presence of incomplete oblique fissures in 71 % of the right lung and in 84 % of the left lungs were higher than most of the studies conducted so far. The percentages of complete oblique fissure in right and left lungs, and complete horizontal fissure in right lung were noticeably low in this study compared to many

studies. Furthermore, absence of horizontal fissure of right lung in nearly twenty percent of the lung examined is also an important finding since the same is reported in very few studies.

This highlights the possibilities of wide range of variations in the lobes and fissures of the lungs and necessitates more research to find out the extend of variations. This study emphasizes the fact that surgeons should be aware of wide range of variations while performing segmental resection and lobectomy to minimize the mortality and morbidity associated with these invasive surgeries. Similarly, this study provides more insights to the radiologist for accurate interpretation of chest x-ray and CT scans.

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